

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON PHYTOCHEMISTRY AND PHARMACOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF *ACHYRANTHES ASPERA* LINN- A TRADITIONAL MEDICINAL HERB

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ABSTRACT

Achyranthes aspera, also known as "Chirchita" in Hindi and "Prickly Chaff Flower" in English, Amaranthaceae family, is a medicinal perennial, erect, 0.3-0.9m, tall herb that grows as a weed along roadsides in India. Traditionally, roots, shoots, leaves, and seeds are used for medicinal purposes in different medical practices like Ayurveda, Siddha or Unani. In Indigenous system this plant is used for the treatment of dysentery, diarrhoea, haemorrhoids, rheumatitis, asthma, skin problems, for improving appetite and several other gastric disorders, toothache leprosy, antifertility, cough. It is also used to treat hydrophobia, snake bites, bleeding piles, cutaneous and ophthalmic disease. Plant is known to possess several secondary metabolites like alkaloids, carbohydrates, saponins, tannins and phenolic compounds, proteins, free amino acids, flavonoids and lignin that are responsible for the different biological activities like antioxidant, antidiabetic,

antihelminthic, spermicidal, antifertility, antipyretic, wound healing, gastroprotective, anticancerous, antimicrobial, antiinflammatory, diuretic, hepatoprotective. This review aims to summarize the phytochemical, and pharmacological activities of *A.aspera* as documented in published studies to assist researchers in future work.

KEYWORDS: *Achyranthes aspera*, Botanical, Phytochemical, Pharmacological activity.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani are traditional practices used since ancient time that wholly depends on natural products derived from plants and their by-products. These practices show

potential against several dreaded diseases including recent global pandemic COVID-19.^[1] Now a days, these natural medicines provide health care to the 65% to 80% of population in developing countries, and developed countries are also fascinated by these medicines due to their efficacy, reliability, cost-effectiveness and no or very less side effects.^[2] More than 20,000 species of medicinal plants have been identified and listed by the WHO that have vital role in the development of potent therapeutic agents.^[3] According to WHO, around 25% of drugs originates from plants while others are artificially made based on plant derived chemicals.^[4] In the recent past, use of plant-based products has increased enormously resulting in the exponential growth of these products globally. Plants release various secondary metabolites like alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, essential oils etc, that have defensive role against natural pests, microorganisms and insects, that are the major sources of pharmaceuticals, food additives and fragrances, therefore, several plant products are being evaluated based on their traditional applications, *Achyranthes aspera* Linn. is a that plant belongs to Amaranthaceae family, and is commonly known as “Prickly Chaff Flower” in English or “Chirchita” in Hindi is one of them. It is 0.3-0.9m tall, erect, perennial herb that grows on roadsides, field boundaries and waste places.^{[5][6]} The different parts of plant exhibit diverse medicinal properties attributed to the presence of various secondary metabolites such as flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, terpenoids, coumarins and reducing sugars. These bioactive compounds play a crucial role in therapeutic applications and can serve as a foundation for the discovery and development of novel pharmaceutical products. Their pharmacological potential underscores the importance of this plant in traditional medicine and modern drug research. In India, *A.aspera* holds a dual significance in both spiritual and medicinal practices. The plant is considered sacred in several Indian traditions and is often used in rituals. Its stems are traditionally employed to sprinkle holy water during purification ceremonies in Hindu households. In rural India, the plant is believed to ward off energies and is sometimes tied to doorways or used in protective rituals. It is also used in offerings to deities symbolizing purity and devotion. *A.aspera* is commonly used to prepare herbal tea valued for its medicinal benefits by boiling leaves, roots or seeds often combined with other herbs for enhanced efficacy. The tea helps in relieving bloating, indigestion and constipation, acts as natural cleanser aiding in the removal of toxins from the body, helps in strengthening the immune system and alleviate symptoms of cold, cough and asthma. The tea is widely consumed in rural areas, reflecting the integration of traditional knowledge into daily life. The phytochemicals achyranthine, ecdysterone, betaine, hentriacontane, saponins A, B, C, D etc, and others are reported to have a variety of biological activities like anti-microbial,

chemoprotective, hepatoprotective, analgesic, anti-arthritic, anti-malarial, hypolipidemic, diuretic, anti-inflammatory, nephroprotective, immunomodulatory, spermicidal, anti-fertility, anti-diabetic.^{[5][6]} This review aims to summarize the phytochemical and pharmacological properties of *A.aspera* (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Pharmacological activities of *A. aspera*.

Taxonomic classification^[7]

- **Kingdom:** Plantae
- **Subkingdom:** Tracheobinota
- **Super Division:** Spermatophyta
- **Division:** Mangoliophyta
- **Class:** Mangoliophsida
- **Subclass:** Caryophyllidae
- **Order:** Caryophyllales
- **Family:** Amaranthaceae
- **Genus:** *Achyranthes*
- **Species:** *aspera*

Botanical description

Achyranthes aspera also known as Chirchita, is around 1.2m tall perennial erect herb with green papery leaves (1.5-7cm long, 0.4-4cm wide) that are obovate or ovate, opposite and

hairy on both sides; a branched stem covered with short hairs; cylindrical roots having secondary and tertiary tap root system that are yellow-brown in colour; flowers arranged in spikes, bracteate and green or red in colour, hypogynous, 5-stamens, 7 gynoecium bicarpellary, syncarpous, superior ovary; brown coloured seed, endospermic rounded at base and truncate at apex.^{[8][9][10]} It is an erect, stiff plant that grows as a weed in India, Asia and many other parts of the world like Africa, Mexico, Central America, Ceylon, and Baluchistan. In India, usually found on the roadside, field boundaries, waste places and can grow in semi-shade or absence of shade. It usually requires moist soil but prefers light sandy, medium loamy heavy clay soils for their growth.^[10] This plant is known by their different names like in Hindi and Unani as Chirchita, Latjeera; Sanskrit as Apamargh; Marathi as Aghada; Tamil as Nayuruvi; Telugu as Antisha, Utareni.^[7]

Phytochemistry of plant

Several components of the plants are responsible for the treatment of various diseases that are either chronic or acute. These components were reported in different studies. Reddy *et al.*, 2012 reported presence of alkaloids, carbohydrates, saponins, tannins and phenolic compounds, proteins and free amino acids, flavonoids and lignin in the alcoholic and aq. extract of *A.aspera*.^[11] As different parts of plant have different phytoactive compounds that are responsible for their biological activities like antioxidant, antidiabetic, antihelminthic, spermicidal, antifertility etc. Vardharaj and Kuppan, 2015 reported 15 active phytochemicals from the alcoholic extract of *A.aspera* by GC-MS analysis with their retention time, this include majorly tetradecane (0.62%), benzaldehyde, 4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethoxy-(0.52%), 3-buten-2-one, 4-(2,2,6-trimethyl-7-oxabicyclo [4.1.0] hept-1-yl) (2.65%), xanthoxylin (0.53%), phenol,4-(3-hydroxy-1propenyl)-2-methoxy-(2.95%), patchouli alcohol (0.76%), dl-(2-fluorophenyl)-glycine (2.18%), flurenol butyl ester (0.91%), hexadecanoic acid, ethyl ester (3.28%), ethanone, 2-(benzoyloxy)-1-(1,1'-biphenyl)-4-yl- (0.93%), phytol (22.13%), 9,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-(12.74%), 9,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)-,2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester (1.12%), squalene (0.55%), and lupeol (1.74%).^[12] From the whole plant of *A.aspera* Laddha *et al.*, 2005 isolated 2 active phytochemical compound i.e., 20-Hydroxyecdysone and phytoecdysteroid.^[13] Another water soluble compound, "Betaine" was also reported by Kapoor and Singh (1966).^[14] This compound was also isolated from dried seeds of *A.aspera* by Desai *et al.*, 2013 that were characterized by IR, NMR, and MS.^[15]

Banerji *et al.*, 1970 isolated a triterpenoid *i.e.*, Ecdysterone from the methanolic extract of *A.aspera* roots that mimics the insect molting hormonal activity, also reported from the whole plant extract.^[16] In another study sharma *et al.*, 2009 reported 6 active compounds from the ethanolic extract of *A.aspera* roots *i.e.* Strigmasta-5, 22-dien-3- β -ol, Trans-13-docasenoic acid, n-Hexacos-14-enoic acid, n-Hexacosanyl-n-decaniate, n-Hexacos-17-enoic acid, n-Hexacos-11-enoic acid.^[17] Anand *et al.*, 2017 also reported 3 terpenoid compounds *i.e.*, Ursolic acid, Corrosolic acid and Achyrantheric acid from the roots of *A.aspera* and showed their potent anticancerous activity against HT-29 cancer cell line.^[18]

From the shoot of *A.aspera*, Misra *et al.*, 1991 and 1992 isolated an essential oil, an alcohol 17-pentatriacontanol and a ketone 36, 47- dihydroxyhenpentacontan-4-one.^{[19][20]} It is also reported that the oil have antifungal activity against *Aspergillus carneus*.^[19] In 1993, Misra *et al.*, also reported 2 new long chain compounds *i.e.*, 16-hydroxy-26-methylheptacosan-2-one and 27-Cyclohexyl-heptacosan-7-ol.^[21] Ali in 1993 were also characterized 4 compounds from the stem *i.e.*, pentatriacontane, 6-pentatriacontane, hexatriacontane and tritriacontane).^[22] In another study, Aziz *et al.*, 2005 isolated 3-Acetoxy-6-benzoyloxy apangamide(I) from the ethyl acetate extract of *A.aspera* stem and their structure were elaborated by modern spectroscopic techniques.^[23]

From the methanolic extract of aerial parts of *A.aspera* O.Kunert *et al.*, 2000 reported 3 Bisdesmosidic saponins (I-III), 20-hydroxyecdysone and quercitin-3-O- β -D-galactoside.^[24] Beside these 3 Bisdesmosidic saponins, Michl *et al.*, 2000 were also isolated 2 new bisdesmosidic triterpenoid saponins from the MeOH extract of aerial parts *i.e.*, \hat{I}^2 -D-glucopyranosyl $3\hat{I}^2$ -[O- \hat{I}^{\pm} -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 $\hat{\alpha}$ '3)-O- \hat{I}^2 -D-glucopyranuronosyloxy]machaerinate (1) and \hat{I}^2 -D-glucopyranosyl $3\hat{I}^2$ -[O- \hat{I}^2 -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 $\hat{\alpha}$ '2)-O- \hat{I}^{\pm} -D-glucopyranuronosyloxy]machaerinate (2) and \hat{I}^2 -D-glucopyranosyl $3\hat{I}^2$ [O- \hat{I}^{\pm} -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 $\hat{\alpha}$ '3)-O- \hat{I}^2 -D-glucopyranuronosyloxy]oleanolate (3), \hat{I}^2 -D-glucopyranosyl $3\hat{I}^2$ -[O- \hat{I}^2 -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 $\hat{\alpha}$ '2)-O- \hat{I}^2 -D-glucopyranuronosyloxy]oleanolate (4), and \hat{I}^2 -D-glucopyranosyl $3\hat{I}^2$ -[O- \hat{I}^2 -D-glucopyranuronosyloxy]oleanolate (5) by NMR spectroscopy.^[25]

Sultana *et al.*, 2018 isolated a yellow mass *i.e.*, Aromadendrene-15-oyl ferulate from the leaves of *A.aspera* that showed positive response to phenolic test and have UV absorption maxima at 274nm.^[26] In another study, VP and Muthuswami, 2020 by the use of GC-MS analysis reported 15 measure bioactive compounds from ethanolic extract of *A.aspera* leaf

i.e., Butanoic acid, 2-oxo- (0.97%), Phytol, acetate (17.05%), 1-Butanol, 3-Methyl- (1.74%), (+)-Lavandulol acetate (0.97%), 6-Octen-1-ol, 3,7 Dimethyl-, Propanoate (3.01%), Decanoic acid (3.39%), 6-Methylfuro[2,3-C]pyrid5-one (3.19%), 3,7,11,15-Tetramethyl-2-hexadecen-1-ol (22.31%), 2-Decen-1-ol (4.06%), 3-Bromo-2Methoxycyclohexanone (4.04%), 2-Nonen-1-ol (2.06%), Cyclohexane, 1-Methyl-2-Methylene-, 5-Deutero- (1.68%), 1 Hexadecyne (14.43%), 6-Octen-1-ol, 3,7 Dimethyl-, Propanoate (10.71%), 6-Octen-1-ol, 3,7 Dimethyl-, Propanoate (9.85%).^[27] Another GC-MS analysis of methanolic extract of *A.aspera* leaf were done by Prakash, 2022 and found 12 major peaks, among them Phytol(21.99%), 9,12-Octadecatrienoic acid(13.74%) and 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, methyl ester(13.35%) were major compounds.^[28]

From the seeds of *Achyranthes aspera* several active compounds were reported. Hariharan et al., 1970 identified 2 saponins i.e., Saponin A characterised as α -L-rhamnopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucuronopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3)-oleanolic acid (VI) and Saponin B as the β -D-galactopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 28) ester of saponin A (VII).^[29] Saponins have antiobesity, hypolipidemic, antioxidative and hepatoprotective effects in high cholesterol fed albino rats.^{[30][31]} Saponin rich fractions also show therapeutic effects against the progression of adjuvant induced arthritis in rats studied by Kothavade et al., 2015.^[32] These also have anti-urolithiatic activity revealed by efficiently dissolution of Calcium oxalate renal stones studied by Rajeshwari et al., 2023.^[33] By HPLC analysis Tamanna Talreja et al., 2017 also reported 3 other saponins i.e., Gitogenin, Diosgenin and Kryptogenin.^[34]

Pharmacological properties of plant

Traditional medicinal uses

In ethical communities, *Achyranthes aspera* is a highly valued herbal medicinal plant for the treatment of no. of diseases. The whole plant juice is used for the cure of dysentery, diarrhoea, haemorrhoids, rheumatitis, skin problems, toothache; their ash used as tooth powder for teeth, when mixed with *Smilax ovalifolia* roots, it improves appetite and several other gastric disorders. A fresh piece of root used as a toothbrush, their powder used in treatment of diarrhoea, leprosy, antifertility, cough, ascites, anasaria, bleeding in delivery; as an astringent, roots are also used for wounds, stomach pain and abdominal tumor, with buttermilk taken as antifertility drug. The plant's seeds have been used to treat hydrophobia, snake bites, cutaneous and ophthalmic disease, and bleeding piles. Leaf powder used to treat early stages of asthma, their paste used to cure rabies, insect bites, nervous disorders, hysteria and snake

bites. Leaf juice when mixed with opium and water, is used in syphilitic sores, gonorrhoea, bowel complaint, piles, and skin eruption. Leaves and roots also have diuretic and urolithiatic activities. The plants is also useful in treating liver complaints, renal dropsy, bronchitis, urinary calculi and other skin diseases and also have tranquillizing properties.^{[7][35][36][37]}

Antioxidant activity

Oxidative stress is a primary factor responsible for several degenerative diseases such as cancer, atherosclerosis, ulcers and others.^[38] Antioxidants are compounds that prevent the oxidation of molecules when exposed to reactive oxygen species (ROS) or free radicals. Priya *et al.*, 2010 investigated the antioxidant property of *Achyranthes aspera* stem in vitro, using methanolic and aqueous extracts, discovered that methanolic extract has higher antioxidative activity than aqueous extract and as dose increases DPPH radical scavenging activity also increases.^[39] In vitro antioxidative properties of *A.aspera* root in different polar solutions were also studied by Purushotham *et al.*, 2013, who noted antioxidative capacity in decreasing order i.e., Ethyl acetate> Methanol>Dichloromethane>Hexane and at 200 µg/ml ethyl acetate root extract has maximum radical scavenging activity up to 93%, followed by methanol extract 91%.^[38] Sharma *et al.*, 2014 also demonstrated that the maximum antioxidative capacities of ethanolic extract of inflorescence and chloroform extract of roots are 426.14mg/g and 417.84mg/g, respectively.^[40] Kumar *et al.*, 2017 also reported that the ethanolic extract of leaves showed the highest DPPH radical scavenging activity and hexane extract had the lowest.^[41]

Thrombolytic activity

Thrombolysis is the breakdown of blood clots formed in blood vessels, used in medication for stroke, myocardial infarction, and acute pulmonary embolism. Raut *et al.*, 2021 has been reported that at 30.5µg/ml dose of methanol extract of stem leaves of *A.aspera* decreased the concentration of DPPH by 50% (IC50) in comparison to standard and also noted 7.29% and 15.35% clot lysis at 10mg/ml and 25mg/ml, respectively. This study has shown that the methanolic extract of *Achyranthes aspera* has potent thrombolytic activity.^[42]

Anti-microbial activity

Antimicrobials are those compounds that inhibit the growth of bacteria, prevent the formation of microbial colonies, and may destroy microorganisms. Yadav *et al.*, 2016 tested the antibacterial activity of an aqueous extract of *A.aspera* root and stem against *Streptococcus mutans* using the cup-plate method and discovered that the maximum zone of inhibition for

the stem is 16mm at 10% concentration and 250µl volume, while the standard shows a 19mm zone of inhibition at 0.2% concentration and 10µl volume and also suggested that this may be due to the presence of alkaloids and tannins in the extract.^[43] Lavanya *et al.*, 2017 studied the antibacterial activity of different extracts of *A.aspera* leaves against *Bacillus subtilis*, *E.coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Enterobacter cloacae* and found diethyl ether extract was most effective and other solvents were ineffective against *B.subtilis* and also noted that *Enterobacter cloacae* is more susceptible and *Bacillus subtilis* is more resistant.^[44] Unissa *et al.*, 2017 also noticed the antimicrobial activity of an aq. extract of root and stem against *Vibrio alginolyticus*.^[45]

Antifertility effect

Antifertility agents are those that prevent ovulation and implantation, destroy zygote or cause abortion in females and prevent spermatogenesis, inhibit testosterone, and mortality of sperm in males. Paul *et al.*, 2010 studied the spermicidal activity of an extract of *A.aspera* in humans and rats and noticed that n-hexane fraction is the most effective and the chloroform extract is least by showing their effectiveness for sperm immobilisation, sperm viability, acrosome status, loss of plasma membrane integrity, 5'-nucleotidase activity, and nuclear chromosome decondensation.^[46] Anuja *et al.*, 2011 also noticed the spermicidal activity of Achyranthine isolated from the roots of *A.aspera* at 150µg of dose in rats.^[47] Kumar *et al.*, 2010 investigated the antifertility effects of total alkaloids from *A.aspera* on fertility in male albino rats by significantly lowering the wt. of testis and accessory glands, and sperm counts.^[48] According to Abu *et al.*, 2014 a hydroethanolic extract of *A.aspera* roots reduces the degeneracy of Leydig cells, spermatogenesis, no. of spermatozoa, blocking of seminal vesicles and prostrate secretions, shrinkage of seminiferous tubules in the testis, decreased testosterone level and reduction in level of several enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants and when treated male rat mate with female rat, implantation site also gets reduced.^[49] When ethanolic extract of *A.aspera* was administered to female rats at 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg bw, Gurumani *et al.*, 2014 observed a decrease in the duration of the estrous and metestrous phase, an increase in the diestrous and proestrous phases, and decrease in the wt. of ovaries and no. of implantation sites in comparison to control.^[50] Prasad *et al.*, 2011 also show effect of ash from *A.aspera* on the reproductive fitness of *Drosophilla melanogaster* and found a decrease in fecundity, fertility, development time, ovariole no., hatchability and viability in adult feeding compared to larval feeding.^[51]

Antidiabetic activity

Diabetes mellitus is one of the most common diseases that severely affect millions of people around the world. It is a condition where insulin is absent, deficient, or defective which ultimately leads to an increase in glucose in the blood and urine. Talukdar *et al.*, 2012 noticed that at dose of 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *A.aspera*, there was a significant reduction in blood glucose levels in alloxan induced diabetic mice which support the anti-hyperglycemic activity of extract and suggests that it may be due to diminished oxidative stress as the activity of catalase and reduced NO levels in diabetic mice.^[51] Kamalakannan *et al.*, 2015 noticed lower blood glucose levels, an increase in glucokinase activity, a decrease in lipid peroxidation and an elevation in reduced glutathione levels in diabetic rats when 250mg/kg ad 500mg/kg doses of an aq. extract of *A.aspera* leaf were administered.^[52] Geeth K, 2016 also noticed decreased blood sugar and cholesterol level when ethanol extract of *A.aspera* leaf were administered to alloxan induced diabetic mice.^[53] Une *et al.*, 2021 also found fall in blood glucose level, normal level of insulin and expression of GLUT-2 and minimal destruction of Islets of Langerhans and β -cells becomes normal in STZ (streptozotocin) induced diabetic rat model when an ethyl acetate dissolved fraction of methanol extract of *A.aspera* administered.^[54] All these findings suggest protective nature of ethanolic extract of *A.aspera* against Diabetes mellitus.

Anthelmintic activity

Helminthiasis is a common disease in the world. Several plant-based treatments are used for parasitic infections. Naga Bharathi *et al.*, 2013 investigated the anthelmintic activity of aq. and methanolic extracts of *A.aspera* stem at different dose and discovered that at dose of 20mg/ml, paralysis ranging from loss of motility to response against external stimuli that gradually leads to death, and methanolic extract were comparatively more active than aq. extract against *Pheretima posthuma* and this may be due to presence of aliphatic compound dihydroxyketone 36,37-dihydroxyhenpentacontan-4-on and triacontanol because of their neurotoxic action.^[55] Esther *et al.*, 2018 also found that aq. extract of *A.aspera* stem has better anthelmintic activity followed by ethyl acetate and least in ethanol extract against *Pheretima posthuma*.^[56]

Anti-inflammatory activity

Inflammation is a defensive response against xenobiotics while uncontrolled inflammatory response is the main cause of continuum disorder like allergies, cardiovascular dysfunctions,

autoimmune disease syndrome, cancer, metabolic syndrome. Several synthetic drugs are available but with several side effects, thus we need natural plant based drugs that have no side effects. Amrutia *et al.*, 2011 studied anti-inflammatory action of different fractions of ethanolic extract of *A.aspera* leaves and found that ethyl acetate fraction was found to be most effective.^[57] Aqueous extract of *A.aspera* leaves and whole plant in albino mice induced with left hind paw edema shows inflammatory activity at 800mg/kg bw more significantly as compared to standard and control group studied by Bhosale *et al.*, 2012.^[58] Aafrin *et al.*, 2018 by Human RBC membrane stabilization method assessed that at 300µg/ml dose of aq. and ethanolic extract of whole plant *A.aspera* showed significant anti-inflammatory activity as compared to standard.^[59] Mengie *et al.*, 2021 also studied *in vivo* wound healing and anti-inflammatory activities of solvent fraction of 80% methanol leaf extract of *A.aspera* in rats and found chloroform fraction be the most active fraction as showing high percentage of wound contraction and reduced period of epithelialization and at 400mg/kg showed highest percentage edema inhibition 52.50% at 4hr post induction.^[60] The mechanism by which EEAA (ethanolic extract of *A.aspera*) inhibits inflammation has been studied by J.-O. Lee *et al.*, 2017 and found that EEAA targets Src and Syk Kinases, suppress NF-κB signaling cascade and activation of transcription factor that results in downregulation of several proinflammatory mediators.^[61]

Diuretic

Diuretics are drugs that are responsible for increasing rates of urine flow, ions for adjusting the volume and composition of body fluids. Naturally occurring diuretics include caffeine in coffee, tea and cola that inhibit Na⁺ reabsorption and alcohol in beer, wine inhibit secretion of ADH. Srivastava *et al.*, 2011 reported that at 400mg/kg per oral dose of whole plant methanolic extract of *A.aspera* significantly increased output as well as urinary electrolyte i.e., increased of Na⁺, K⁺ and Cl⁻ ion excretion but was less than standard.^[62] Niranjana *et al.*, 2012 also noted diuretic activity at 100mg/kg bw dose of aq. and alcoholic extracts of *A.aspera* leaf by increase of urine volume, cation and anion excretion.^[63] Diuretic, natriuretic and kaliuretic effects were also studied by Asif *et al.*, 2014 at 50mg/kg of dose of crude aq. extract of plant.^[64] Warke *et al.*, 2018 also noticed diuretic effect of Petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, alcoholic and aq. extract of *A.aspera* leaves when administered in rats.^[65]

Anxiolytic activity

Anxiety is one of the psychiatric disorders. In the traditional medical system, a variety of herbal plants have been used to treat anxiety disease. Barua et al, 2012 demonstrate anxiolytic activity by significant increase in no. of rearing, assisted rearing and no. of square travelled in open field test; increased time spent and no. of crossing and decreased duration of immobility in light box in light/dark exploration test (LDE) and increased no. and duration of head poking in hole board test at 100, 300 and 600 mg/kg doses of methanolic extract of *A.aspera* leaves shown.^[66] The anxiolytic activity of a hydroalcoholic extract of *A.aspera* leaf was also evaluated in mice using open field test, hole board test, and light/dark exploration test at 300 mg/kg and 600 mg/kg extract doses and it was suggested that this activity may be due to GABA A-BZD complex.^[67]

Antiatherosclerotic activity

Atherosclerosis is a disease of the arteries where fats, cholesterol and other substance build up in and on the arterial wall, which may lead to the blocking of blood flow. Sharma et al., 2013 studied anti-atherosclerotic activity at 100, 200 and 400mg/kg of ethanol extract of *A.aspera* while 10 mg/kg dose of saponins was administered in rats with a hyperlipidemic diet and found a decrease in total cholesterol, total glyceride, low density lipoprotein, serum glucose and atherogenic index increased significantly in comparison to only HD (hyperlipidemic diet) fed rats that were responsible for atherosclerosis.^[68]

Wound Healing activity

In burn wound rat models using ointment compounded with a 5% methanolic extract of *A.aspera* leaves, Barua et al., 2012 discovered wound contraction, an increased no. of antioxidative enzymes, vitamin C, prohealing and biochemical parameters like hydroxyproline and protein content than control; up regulation of matrix metalloproteases (MMP-2 and -9) plays a role in remodelling of extracellular matrix. Histologically collagen deposition, fibroblast proliferation and epidermis formation from tissue granulation were all observed in *A.aspera* treated animals.^[69] Modal et al, 2016 investigated the wound healing activity of an ethanolic extract of *A.aspera* seeds and discovered that it improved wound contraction, epithelialization wound breaking strength, antioxidant enzymes and connective tissue markers.^[70] Rajendran, 2021 investigated the wound healing activity of an aqueous extract of the whole plant *A.aspera* in wistar albino rat excision wounds discovering significant healing activity, increased infiltration of inflammatory cells, fibroblasts and

epithelialisation, and moderate toxicity. GC-MS analysis of extract showed presence of stearic, oleic, linoleic, and ascorbic acid that play an important role in wound healing by increasing VEGF- α , IL-1 β and decreased in TF- α with proangiogenic and anti-inflammatory effect.^[71] Nigusse et al., 2022 also evaluated the wound healing activity of *A.aspera* extract by DPPH radical scavenging activity and cell proliferation activity and found 95% inhibitors of ROS at 10 mg/ml and 44% increase in human epidermal keratinocyte multiplication, respectively.^[72]

Gastroprotective effect

Das et al., 2012 also studied the antiulcer activity of an ethanolic extract of *A.aspera* leaves in pyloric ligated and ethanol induced ulcerated rats and the decrease in stomach acidity, volume of gastric content and pH may be due to the presence of flavonoids and tannins in the extract.^[73] It is also reported by Mishra et al., 2014 that an ethanolic extract of *A.aspera* leaves found maximum protection at 200 mg/kg, p.o in the CRU models, a reduction in free and total acidity in pyloric ligation model and an increased gastric mucin level that exerts significant protection in ethanol and aspirin induced gastric lesions in rats.^[74]

Hepatoprotective effect

BK Manjunatha et al., 2012 studied hepatoprotective effect of ethanolic extract of *A.aspera* seeds on CCL4 induced liver damage in rats and noticed that at 100mg/kg, p.o inhibit increase in serum levels of total bilirubin, protein serum alanine transaminase, aspartate transaminase and alkaline phosphatase that reflects liver protection.^[75] According to Fahim et al., 2018 increased SGPT and bilirubin in liver damaged rats caused by CCl4 were significantly reversed when treated with a methanolic extract of *A.aspera* roots but not when treated with *A.aspera* bark.^[76] Tae Woo Oh et al., 2019 also noticed a decrease in body weight, reduction in expression of ACC1, FAS, SCD-1, pPAR γ mRNA and high hepatic expression of PAMPK/AMPK in HA diet mice when treated with an extract of *A.aspera* in comparison to HF diet mice.^[77]

Anticancer activity

Cancer is an uncontrollable growth of the body's cell that spreads to other parts of the body. Treatment of cancer is costly and has very severe side effects. PR Subbarayan et al., 2012 studied the anticancerous effect of *A.aspera* leaf extract when administered in athymic mice for 32 days intraperitoneally and noticed a reduction in tumor weight and volume, an increase in caspase-3 mRNA and suppressed expression of prosurvival kinase Akt-1 that confirmed

apoptosis induction in tumor cells.^[78] Arora et al., 2014 also investigated the antitumor effect of ethanolic and aqueous root extracts of *A.aspera* on the growth of colon cancers and found the aqueous extract had greater cytotoxic activity against COLO-205 cells.^[79] Anticancer activity of 70% ethanolic extract of *A.aspera* L. roots has also been investigated in vitro against different human cancer cell lines at 100 µg/ml of dose by Shivsaran singh et al., 2017.^[80] It has also been found that *A.aspera* root extract was most cytotoxic, causing about 90% inhibition of HeLa cells by Omidiani et al., 2020 in comparison to different extracts of *A.aspera* leaf, stem, and root in ethyl acetate, acetone, ethanol and methanol.^[81] Rishi Kant Sigh et al., 2021 also studied the effects of a methanolic extract of *A.aspera* leaf on Dalton's Lymphoma in vitro and vivo and found suppressed cell proliferation, decreased mitochondrial membrane potential, changed morphological structure and induced mitochondrial apoptosis in Dalton's Lymphoma cells by suppressing the PKC signalling pathway.^[82]

CONCLUSION

Herbs play an important role in the treatment of various diseases in our traditional practices. In this review, phytochemical, and pharmacological evaluation of *Achyranthes aspera* in various polar and non-polar extracts was tested for the presence of compounds such as alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, phenolics, saponins, and steroids. These constituents have a vital role in the treatment of a number of diseases, including arthritis, infectious diseases, cancer, anxiety, obesity, diabetes, wound healing, asthma, and snakebite. Thus, *A.aspera* is a multipurpose medicinal agent. Its findings pave the way for further investigation and research to identify the active chemical responsible for the plant's biological activity and to comprehend the precise mechanism of action by which they exert their biological effects.

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